

STRUCTURAL MAGNETIC COMPOSITES FOR USE IN ELECTRO-MECHANICAL APPLICATIONS

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the development of a fibre reinforced polymer composite laminate with both magnetic and mechanical functionality. Epoxy resin films containing pure iron particles in 0 – 30% volume fractions were incorporated into glass fibre composite laminates as a means of increasing magnetic permeability. Particle-films showed good adhesion with fibre-reinforced plies, with a 5% reduction in interlaminar shear strength upon their introduction. Material property characterisation determined the mechanical and magnetic properties of different volume fraction particle-resins. Classical laminate analysis was then applied to show the effect of their incorporation on the global mechanical properties of a glass fibre laminate.

1 INTRODUCTION

While Fibre Reinforced Polymer Composites (FRPC) meet the structural demands for the design and manufacture of electromagnetic machines, their low magnetic susceptibility generally limits the potential performance of these machines. For example, Surface-Mounted Permanent Magnet (SMPM) machines, in which magnets are bonded to the outer surface of a back iron, display high power density and efficiency, but cannot withstand the forces experienced during high-speed rotation. Containment is required and usually consists of FRPC overbanding [1,2] or a non-magnetic metallic sleeve [3,4]. Since these materials are magnetically inert, their inclusion introduces a large effective air-gap, reducing the magnetic loading of the machine.

The effect of this may be reduced by increasing the magnetic permeability of the containment sleeve. Yon *et al.* [5] demonstrated an improvement in the fundamental component of air-gap flux density with the use of a semi-permeable containment sleeve. For the electrical machine example considered, and assuming idealised isotropic magnetic characteristics, an optimal sleeve relative permeability of approximately 7 could result in a 28% increase in the fundamental component of air-gap flux density. The material applied however is a 50% cold worked AISI 304L stainless steel, which displayed high mechanical strength, but limited permeability of approximately 2.6. It also possesses low electrical resistivity, and a laminated assembly had to be employed to reduce eddy current losses, making it complex and expensive to manufacture. Different machine designs may also be expected to have different optimal sleeve permeability values, so a material with a fixed set of properties would not be suitable in all cases.

The aim herein is to develop a multi-functional fibre reinforced composite with embedded magnetic properties, as an alternative to the metallic containment sleeve discussed above. The mechanical strength and magnetic permeability may then be tailored to meet the requirements of various different electro-mechanical applications.

There are a number of options available for introducing magnetic properties into a FRPC, including high permeability sheet, mesh and particulate materials. In this work, particulate material was selected as particle separation in the laminate is expected to maintain high electrical resistivity, limiting eddy

current losses. There is also a large body of work investigating the effects of particulate incorporation into FRPC for a variety of different applications, including electromagnetic interference shielding [6,7], density variation [8] and toughening [9,10].

In this case, particle-films have been applied for incorporation into preimpregnated (prepreg) glass fibre laminates. This form of particle incorporation was selected for its compatibility with existing prepreg manufacturing methods, and allows for flexible positioning of the material within the laminate. This paper focusses on determining the properties of these films, and investigates the effect of their incorporation into a fibre composite laminate with respect to the mechanical properties of the resulting assembly.

2 PARTICLE-FILM MANUFACTURE

A mould was constructed for film manufacture, with adhesive shims applied to a Freekote™ coated polyimide sheet to restrict resin flow and control film thickness (~150 µm), as shown in Figure 1. Excess resin-particle mixtures were dropped into the centre of the shim-bounded area and heated to 50°C to promote resin flow. This was then topped with a second Freekote™ coated polyimide sheet and transferred to a hot press where the films were part-cured for one hour at 50°C under a pressure of approximately 1.9 MPa.

Figure 1: Method of particle-film manufacture.

3 MATERIAL TESTING

In order to determine the material properties of individual particle-film layers, large volume samples were manufactured and tested.

Particle-resin mixtures consisted of epoxy resin (Epon 828, Momentive) with high viscosity curing agent (Epikure 3115A, Momentive). Pure iron particles, 30-50 µm diameter, were then added in volume fractions ranging from 0% to 30%.

3.1 Particle-Resin Properties

Tensile testing was carried out to determine mechanical properties of the different volume fraction materials. Six dog bone samples of different particle volume fraction resin mixtures were manufactured and tested according to ASTM standard 638 [11]. Tests were performed on a Shimadzu AGS-X universal testing machine with a 1 kN calibrated load cell. Displacement control of 2 mm/min was applied and strain measurements were performed throughout using video extensometry.

Magnetic testing was carried out to determine the relative permeability of different volume fraction materials. A series of toroid samples were manufactured containing different particle volume fractions and tested according to standard EN 60404-6:2003 [12]. Each toroid was wrapped with a search coil consisting of approximately 500 turns of evenly distributed 0.22 mm copper wire. This was followed by

an excitation coil of approximately 780 turns of evenly distributed 1.0 mm copper wire. Current applied to the excitation coil, I_E , and voltage measured in the search coil, U_S , were recorded and used to calculate relative permeability, μ_r , as follows:

$$\mu_r = \frac{B}{\mu_0 H} \quad (1)$$

where magnetic flux density, $B = \frac{1}{N_S A} \int U_S dt$ (2)

and magnetic field strength, $H = \frac{I_E N_E}{l_m}$ (3)

where N_E and N_S are the number of turns of the excitation and search coils respectively, A is the cross-sectional area of the sample, and l_m is the mean magnetic path length.

3.2 Glass Fibre Composite Properties

Tensile testing was carried out to determine mechanical properties of the glass fibre composite material (unidirectional E-glass/epoxy 913, Hexcel UK) into which particle-resin films were incorporated. Three separate laminates were manufactured with the following lay-ups; $[0^\circ]_8$ and $[90^\circ]_{16}$, which were tested according to ASTM standard D3039 [13], and $[\pm 45^\circ]_{16}$, which was tested according to ASTM standard D3518 [14]. Each laminate was cut to produce six specimens, with end tabs bonded onto each. Tests on the 90° samples were performed using a Shimadzu AGS-X universal testing machine, with a 10 kN calibrated load. All other samples were tested on a Schenck universal testing machine with a 75 kN calibrated load cell. Displacement control of 2 mm/min was applied and strain measurements were performed throughout using video extensometry.

3.3 Interlaminar Shear Strength

Resin films were manufactured containing different volume fractions of iron particles, as described in Section 2. These were then introduced as the central ply in a unidirectional glass/epoxy fibre composite laminate $[0^\circ]_{16}$, as shown in Figure 3a. Each laminate was cut to produce eight samples for Interlaminar Shear Strength (ILSS) testing, which was carried out according to standard BS EN 2563 [15]. Tests were performed on a Shimadzu AGS-X universal testing machine with a 10 kN calibrated load cell. Displacement control of 1 mm/min was applied and force displacement measurements performed throughout.

4 RESULTS

4.1 Particle-Resin Properties

Ultimate tensile strength (UTS), modulus (E_I) and permeability values for different particle volume fractions are given in Figures 2a and b respectively.

Figure 2: Material properties for resins with varying particle content.

Modulus was seen to increase with increasing particle volume fraction, as would be expected with the introduction of a stiffer phase to a matrix material. UTS would also be expected to increase with particle content, as the matrix transfers some of the load to the high-strength particulate material. However, the results in Figure 2a show no significant difference in UTS for different volume fraction materials. This may be due to increased particle volume fraction increasing the viscosity of the resin, leading to increased air entrainment during mixing. The increased presence of air may then counteract any improvement in strength that would have been bestowed by the presence of the particles. The increased air content may also account for the higher degree of variation observed with increasing volume fraction.

Permeability increases with increasing particle volume fraction, as shown in Figure 2b. However, the data does not display a clear trend, and does not fit with the know relative permeability of 1 at zero particle content. Two different mathematical models were explored for comparative purposes;

Bruggeman [16]:
$$\mu_r = \frac{\mu_m}{(1-x)^3} \quad (4)$$

Böttcher [17]:
$$\mu_r = \frac{\mu_m}{1-3x} \quad (5)$$

Where μ_m , is the permeability of the matrix and x is the particle volume fraction. These models are presented with the experimental data in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Relative permeability for different particle volume fraction materials.

Experimental data agrees relatively well with the Böttcher model for the higher volume fraction test samples, but is significantly different for the 10% test sample. This is likely to be due to inaccuracies in

assessing the geometry of the primary and secondary coils, to which low permeability toroid BH measurement is particularly sensitive.

4.2 Glass Fibre Composite Properties

Material properties for the E-glass/epoxy fibre composite material are given in Table 1.

Property	Engineering constant		Measured value
Modulus 0°	E_1	[GPa]	41.2 (1.7)
Modulus 90°	E_2	[GPa]	12.8 (1.0)
Poisson's ratio	ν_{12}	–	0.39 (0.05)
Shear Modulus	G_{12}	[GPa]	4.0 (0.3)
Tensile Strength 0°	σ_1	[MPa]	962.5 (35.0)
Tensile Strength 90°	σ_2	[MPa]	64.1 (5.3)
Shear Strength	τ_{12}	[MPa]	43.8 (5.4)

Table 1: Material properties for 913 glass fibre composite, with standard deviation in brackets.

4.3 Interlaminar Shear Strength

Microscopy of test samples revealed no evidence of voids or particle migration away from the central ply. A typical optical micrograph is shown in Figure 4a.

Figure 4: a) Optical micrograph and b) Interlaminar Shear Strength for glass fibre composite laminates with central resin film layers containing different particle volume fractions.

Incorporation of a central particle-resin layer results in a small reduction in ILSS (~5%), as shown in Figure 4b, indicating good adhesion between the resin film and fibre composite layers. This reduction also appears to be relatively consistent for different volume fraction films, suggesting that bonding between the layers is independent of filler content.

5 LAMINATE PROPERTY ANALYSIS

The effect of incorporating these particle resin films into a glass fibre composite laminate was explored using Classical Laminate Analysis (CLA), a full description of which may be found in [18]. Analysis was performed using the material properties determined in Section 4 and assuming linear elastic properties with perfect bonding between layers and plane stress. Different numbers of film layers

were distributed evenly in a unidirectional, $[0^\circ]_8$ layup, to produce a symmetric laminate. The highest volume fraction (V_f) of particles (30%) was selected for its high permeability. Modulus in the fibre direction (E_1), and UTS were then calculated for different volume fraction films, using material data from Section 4.1. Results are presented in Table 2.

No. Fibre Layers	Particle-Film Layers		Laminate Thickness (mm)	Bulk Particle V_f (%)	Modulus (GPa) E_1	UTS (MPa) σ_{11}^*
	V_f (%)	No.				
8	-	0	1.12	0	41.2	963
8	30	1	1.26	3.3	37.2	868
8	30	2	1.4	6	34.0	793
8	30	3	1.54	8.2	31.4	731
8	30	4	1.68	10	29.2	680
8	30	5	1.82	11.5	27.3	637
8	30	6	1.96	12.9	25.7	600
8	30	7	2.1	14	24.4	567

Table 2: Results from CLA analysis of different particle and fibre composite layer combinations.

Modulus and UTS of the laminate are both shown to decrease with increasing numbers of additional particle-film layers. Permeability results for different V_f particle-resins presented in Section 4.1 were applied to the bulk particle V_f calculated for each laminate in Table 2, to estimate the permeability that may be expected from each laminate. These results are shown in Figure 5, and compared with the corresponding UTS calculated above.

Figure 5: UTS and estimated permeability for laminates containing different numbers of particle-film layers.

Figure 5 shows an increase in permeability with increasing numbers of particle-film layers, and a decrease in UTS. The permeability increase is small however, so that even with alternating film-fibre layers (8 fibre, 7 film), the expected material permeability is still below 2. UTS appears to be far more significantly affected by the particle-film incorporation, being reduced to 60% for this configuration.

6 CONCLUSIONS

Tailoring the mechanical and magnetic properties of a fibre composite laminate has the potential to provide significant benefits to electro-mechanical machines. In this study, the ability to incorporate

magnetic permeability into a fibre composite laminate has been demonstrated, with good adhesion observed between particle and fibre layers. Increasing inclusions of particle-resin layers, while increasing the bulk permeability of the laminate, also weakened the structure, reducing the modulus and UTS. Essentially there is a trade-off, the selection of which will depend upon the specific application under consideration.

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